

1 **UBE2T is a switch that governs the cell cycle in transformation.**

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6 We describe here a third ubiquitin switch with important functions in cell cycle restriction and immune
7 defense. We recently described the functions of UBE2L6 as a molecular switch that controls expression of
8 class I MHC genes, which tumors modulate to for immune evasion, and UBE2C, which functions as a
9 switch that controls an entire cancer cell gene expression program, including AURKA, TPX2, EZH2, ECT2
10 and others. We discovered the E2 ubiquitin enzyme UBE2T as a regulator of the *CDKN* family of
11 cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors using a systems biological approach combined with reverse genetic
12 methodology. UBE2T regulation of the cell cycle and CDKN genes was influenced by p53 status of the
13 cell. Similar to UBE2C, UBE2T controlled a proliferation program consisting of genes that function in cell
14 cycle progression, related to but separate from its function as a CDKN family inhibitor. CDK4/6 inhibition
15 could override changes in UBE2T expression in p53-deficient backgrounds, suppressing p53
16 status-dependent control of TOP2A. UBE2T is a switch that governs the cell cycle in transformation.

17 **References**

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